

THE CONCEPT OF PATRIOTISM IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK PROVERBS

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Annotation: This article analyzes the proverbs with the dominant concept of the Motherland in the Uzbek folk proverbs belonging to the folklore. In Uzbek and English folk proverbs, the concept of the Motherland is of great importance. In the proverbs of these two peoples, there are differences in the ways of comparing and comparing the Motherland. This is a factor related to the mental characteristics of the people. In our article, these differences and similarities are taken into account and analyzed.

Key words: proverb, "Motherland" concept, methodology, types of proverbs and analysis

As a result of our research, it was noted that proverbs, in particular, Uzbek folk proverbs combine various concepts in their structure. The concept of the homeland is very common in Uzbek folk proverbs. listed. For this reason, proverbs reflecting the concept of the Motherland are often found in folklore, and it is important to analyze it from the point of view of linguistics. The concept of the homeland still attracts linguists with many undiscovered aspects.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

In Russian linguistics in the first half of the 20th century, the philosopher S. Askoldev introduced this concept, which the scientist notes as a communicative process that can lead to communication between representatives of different nationalities. Because when analyzing the conceptual features of a word or term, first of all, the mind and perception come into play. The importance of human perception is very important both in communicating with people, creating a communicative situation, creating a speech strategy and achieving results. Yu.S. Stepanovyo zgan "Концепты" The main object of study of the book "Тонкая пленка цивилизации" is the concept, and the scientist evaluates this concept as a cultural phenomenon similar to the "Concept" related to logic, psychology, philosophy, and from the historical point of view to the "ideas" of Plato. If we look at the similarities between Western and Eastern literature, English and Uzbek proverbs, concepts such as friendship, patriotism, honesty, hard work, kindness, and justice have always been praised in both nations. For

example: Bulbul chamanni sevar- Odam Vatanni. In English, we can say the proverb: Every bird likes its own nest. If we translate this proverb literally, it will be translated in such a way that every bird loves its own nest, and the same meaning of loving the Motherland as the Uzbek proverb will appear, but rather than the translation, the Uzbek equivalent it will be more clear and understandable. Various features of proverbs have been considered by English scholars and suggestions have been made. We can mention Honik, Meider, Norik, Taylor, Arora as scientists who have conducted many researches on English proverbs. They proved the most important aspects of proverbs in science, and mainly paid attention to issues such as their structural structure, the use of artistic tools, their role in social life, and presented them in their works. One of the scientists who made a great contribution to this field, the services of folklorist Maider should be specially noted. Because he is one of the scientists who conducted a lot of research on proverbs and wrote theoretical works. He tried to fully explain the most important aspects of proverbs in his works. And he expresses these thoughts about the proverb: "Proverbs are used in a wide of situations and no limits to the use of the proverb. They can be used to strengthen our arguments, express certain generalizations, influence or manipulate other people, rationalize our own shortcomings, question certain behavioral patterns, satirize social ills, poke fun at ridiculous situations." That is: "Proverbs are widely used and there is no limit to their use. Proverbs strengthen our arguments, strengthen our general and specific ideas, express our general and specific ideas, control or influence other people, and express the evils in society. Also, folklorist scientist Norik says about proverbs, "Proverbs are the informant of an existing event or event" and the unique aspect of proverbs expresses such an opinion about traditionality. The traditional nature of proverbs correlates closely with their status as items of folkloric". As a result of the research of B. Sarimsakov and M. Afzalov, they classify proverbs as follows: in alphabetical order, classification by subject, poetic and historical classification, classification by the structure of proverbs.

1. Alphabetical order. In this case, the available proverbs are collected in alphabetical order. This situation helps the user to find the necessary proverb in the collection faster.
2. Classification by topic. In this type of classification, the material is divided into groups according to certain topics and given in alphabetical order within each group.

3. Poetic classification. In most proverbs, the nature of the meaning changes with the passing of time: the proverbs used in their original meaning can later be used only figuratively. As we mentioned above, this classification identifies proverbs that are used in their own meaning, figuratively, and in both their own and figurative meanings. Proverbs used in the literal sense: "A dry spoon tears the mouth." - Quruq qoshiq og'iz yirtar.

4. Historical classification. Proverb is a very ancient, but at the same time always modern genre. That is why proverbs belong to different periods. "Sand does not accumulate and becomes a stone, slave does not accumulate and becomes a head", - proverbs of slavery. "The fist of a poor man is better than the mouth of an emir." Such proverbs as "The bread of wealth is half", "You will stretch your waist until you reach your back" are now used in a figurative sense. Classification according to the structure of proverbs. In this case, proverbs are divided into several groups depending on the number of logical centers in their content:

a) proverbs with two (component) parts: "A stick that has not landed on an unsaid ground", "Work makes one hungry, a lazy person avoids work",

b) proverbs with four components: Don't leave on the road because there is no woman in the barn.

Don't leave the husband and wife for lack of money.

2. In addition to the compact form of the proverbs, the expression of the idea, and the use of artistic and descriptive means in the proverbs, another feature is the use of artistic and descriptive means in the proverbs. The art of contrast is used more in proverbs. For example, "A friend speaks bitterly, an enemy laughs", "Say a lot, say a little". For example, "Meat and nails cannot be separated." Among the folk proverbs, there are also proverbs against people with negative qualities. For example: "A bad excuse is better than none" from English is translated into Uzbek - to apologize unwillingly is better than not asking at all. An important factor in the process of learning proverbs is its structure, how it is formed through syntactical units. According to the structure of proverbs, they are formed on the basis of one or several syntactic units. Proverbs consisting of one syntactic whole are usually considered to be one-part proverbs, and are often in the form of a figurative sentence. Uzbek and English folk proverbs are very similar in these aspects. We will try to prove our point through the following proverbs.

- The absent is always in the wrong- O'zi yo'qning — ko'zi yo'q.

- There is no accounting for tastes -Har kim suygan oshini ichadi.

- Actions speak louder than words -Gap bilguncha — ish bil.
- Advise none to marry or go to war-Har kimning niyati o'zining yo'ldoshi.

Most proverbs consist of two parts, one of which is descriptive has the essence, the second part consists of the conclusion:

- After dinner sit a while,
After supper walk a mile.
- Qorning ochmasdan ovqat yegin,
- Qorning to'ymasdan qo'l artgin.
- Art is long, life is short.
- Ilmsiz — bir yashar, Ilmli — ming yashar.

The linguistic expression of aphorisms in the Uzbek language, reflecting the feeling of love for the Motherland, would embody the rich cultural and historical heritage of Uzbekistan, as well as a deep sense of attachment to the land and its people. were. As a result of our research, it was noted that proverbs, in particular, Uzbek folk proverbs combine various concepts in their structure. The concept of homeland is very common in Uzbek folk proverbs. . For this reason, proverbs reflecting the concept of the Motherland are often found in folklore, and it is important to analyze it from the point of view of linguistics. The concept of homeland still attracts linguists with many unexplored aspects.

First, the proverb always means a clear, complete thought. This opinion is expressed as a firm, concise conclusion. And intellectual clarity is formed on the basis of a whole composition consisting of two logical centers that allow it to be concisely expressed. That is why the proverb does not contain any redundant words, images or descriptions. Because the simple idea in the proverb itself acquires a great aesthetic essence. Secondly, it is characteristic for a proverb to express a certain idea in logical consistency and strict polarity. Thirdly, the proverb is based on a complete thought. Fourthly, proverbs can be used in their own and figurative sense. This feature expands the thematic range of proverbs and the limits of their application. That is why the proverb is widespread among one or more peoples. Fifth, a proverb is used in speech as a means of proof. In addition, proverbs have common features that apply to other genres of folklore. One of such features is the very slow creation and disappearance of proverbs, the extreme stability of the language. This feature is explained by the direct connection to the formal aspect of the content of the proverb. It is known that not every idea can be a lesson, and not every idea can be a proverb. Therefore, there are certain conditions for an instructive thought to become a proverb.

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